

GRAMMAR TEACHING EXERCISES IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEXTBOOK

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Abstract. This article provides detailed information about the methods of learning and teaching grammar in foreign language classes, and the relationship of grammar with other linguistic departments.

Keywords. Methodology of foreign language teaching, grammar, grammar teaching methods, relationship with other departments of linguistics

The term goal in foreign language methodology can be explained as follows. In order for the type of speech activity to receive the status of a goal, first of all, it must have its own educational content (speech topic, speech skills, language material), secondly, the language material must first be studied in this type of speech activity, and thirdly, time and the main part of the effort is spent, and finally, fourthly, most of the exercises must be done in this type of speech activity. For example: speaking is taught on the basis of a special topic and language material in the first stage, and reading has a similar position in the upper grades. Speaking topics and lexical-grammatical material of the elementary period are repeated and strengthened in reading and writing. The recommended methodological criteria are sufficient for the interpretation of the practical purpose. When teaching the type of speech activity, if the four methodological criteria are not observed, it loses its goal level and takes its place as an educational tool. A foreign language article can be given as an example. The grammatical phenomenon of the article is studied in the following order in the types of speech activity: listening, understanding-» speaking-» writing-» reading. The first and second of them (listening and speaking) are the specific goal of education, and the other two (writing and reading) are educational tools.

Wide use of information technologies is recommended in foreign language education. Therefore, in the process of teaching grammatical phenomena to students, we found it necessary to use the following information technologies: computer technology (internet network), interactive methods, open discussion (dispute), excursion, auction, press conference, competition, round table, wish-intention, she types of riyat, foreign language teaching project method, etc.

A cluster approach or method is also effective in teaching French grammar to students in secondary schools. This method is not only effective, but also a very convenient way to teach students. For example: Based on our special observations and experience, we came to the following conclusions: the use of games and tasks serves as an effective tool in the implementation of practical, educational, general educational and developmental goals of foreign language teaching; allows to eliminate the psychological negative experiences of students in relation to expressing (speaking) in a foreign language, teaches students to think independently, master the acquisition of speech skills, encourages them to achieve goals, to win, language based on communicative methodology allows learning, makes a significant

contribution to attracting all students to the lesson, increasing their interest, and increasing the effectiveness of the lesson.

Knowledge, skills and competence acquire a unique attitude in learning a foreign language and reflect the nature of the educational subject. In order to express an idea or understand the expressed idea in speech, it is necessary to be able to use language material. To achieve this, it is necessary to establish a strong and flexible connection between language tools and speech content, as S. Setlin says, an association. Language skills are formed as part of speaking skills.

The formation of grammatical skills is a three-stage methodology:

- 1) the distribution stage consists of explaining a new grammatical unit (presenting it in a speech sample), explaining and performing preliminary grammatical operations.
- 2) doing grammar exercises. This stage focuses mainly on skill building.
- 3) the stage of using a grammatical phenomenon in the types of speech activity

It is clear from what has been said that grammar serves to develop skills, not to absorb knowledge. The only goal of researching the scientific-methodical description of the formation of English grammar skills in high school students is to introduce a model of teaching English grammar. The theoretical model is a technology for improving students' English grammar skills. The exercises used in foreign language teaching were classified: types of speech activities (speaking/listening/understanding/reading/writing) exercises; language material (vocabulary/ grammar/ pronunciation) exercises; receptive/reproductive exercises; presentation/training/application exercises; familiarization/practice/application/correction (correction) exercises should be conducted. Formative (educational/ informative/ generalization mastery); developmental (skill-forming/operational/training of ready-made material) exercise; it would be appropriate if an improvement (qualification/motivational/acquisition of grammatical movement) exercise was conducted.

The grammatical level of any language consists of grammatical forms of words, phrases and sentences. Grammar, like other levels of language, has its own units. The smallest grammatical unit is a morpheme, words are formed from morphemes, and words, in turn, participate in the construction of phrases and sentences. A sentence is a large and independent unit of grammar. There are also larger units than a sentence: complex syntactic (unit) whole, paragraph and text. The grammatical structure of the language has its own characteristics.

First, the grammatical construction of the language: the structure of the word, rules of inflection and type, word combinations and types of grammar change very slowly as a product of historical development.

Second, grammar is generalizable. For example, words such as cart, school, stone, child have their own lexical meaning, but from a grammatical point of view, these words express the concept of subjectivity and form a noun group. These words are summarized not by their lexical meaning, but by their grammatical meaning.

Morphology and syntax study the grammatical structure of the language. Morphology examines word groups and their grammatical forms. Syntax studies the grammatical structure of speech. In this case, the word is the main unit. Units larger than a sentence are also studied in syntax. The language system consists of language units - phoneme, morpheme, word, sentence and a whole of language levels. It can be seen from the above that the phonetic, lexical, and grammatical aspects of the language, which is a means of communication, is a

system that forms mutual proportions based on certain internal laws. The proportionality that makes up the system is manifested in specific rules. Sentences in a certain language are made up of words, words are made up of syllables, and syllables are made up of speech sounds. In other words, the words that make up the sentence are combined based on the rules of the language. Any combination of words cannot be a sentence. Words gathered in a disordered picture do not serve to express content. The sequence of words is required to be in accordance with a certain order and general rule. This situation itself shows that language is a system. Sounds specific to a certain language make up the phonetic system of that language, the lexical system of words. A word adopted from one language to another is subject to the phonetic system and pronunciation norms of that language.

According to the stage and principles of education, all phenomena included in the language minimum of a general educational school are taught in the following conditions in the types of speech activities:

I. Language material to be mastered in listening comprehension is divided into six categories:

1. The studied language material does not participate in other types of speech activity. It is used later in speaking, later still in writing and reading, but learned in this school year.
2. The language material given for listening comprehension is also said in speaking, writing and reading is used in the next lessons.
3. The unit mastered in listening comprehension is considered as speaking material in this lesson and will be written and read in the next school year.
4. The unit used in listening comprehension and speaking is involved in writing and reading after several grades.
5. The material covered in listening comprehension is not included in other types of speech activities in the foreign language school course.
6. The material found in the audio text is used in this lesson itself (except for the first academic year) in all three types of speech activities.

II. The language material studied in the course consists of six categories:

1. It is not included in reproductive speech at all (used in listening comprehension).
2. It is not included in any type of speech activity other than reading ("lexicon other than novoculary-vocabulary", which is not part of the students' vocabulary).
3. The words necessary to form the content of the graphic text are taught again as new words in the next lessons (if the minimum vocabulary is taken into account).
4. New words of poems and songs learned by imitation are not included in students' oral speech or writing.
5. New words included in reading technique exercises are taught as special new material used in speech activities (if the minimum vocabulary is taken into account).
6. Words that are practiced in listening and speaking after reading are not practiced in writing.

III. Language material involved in speaking is also studied in all other types of speech activity. They are language material called active lexicon and grammar.

IV. Separate language material is not given for expressing a written opinion, because writing is not the goal of foreign language teaching, it is an educational tool. Only a part of the language units learned in oral speech is practiced in writing. The limited use of language material in the types of speech activity is a methodical law applicable not only to the foreign language, but also to the mother tongue and the second language. That is why methodical

rules were issued about receptive and reproductive speech, active and passive language material.

Theoretical and experimental studies show that language material can be mastered in different lessons, apart from the limited use of language material in the types of speech activities, the use, meaning and form of each language unit, and even the sound and graphic aspects of the form are separated. The principle of teaching the material by different types of speech activity is taken into account when creating a methodological typology of the language material.

The methodological phenomenon called foreign language unit consists of a number of small concepts. They are listed below:

1. Vocabulary unit - root word; artificial word;
2. Lexical unit - root word; artificial word (if the word or word-forming elements in its content are not studied separately); word-forming element (affix); fixed phrase; a sentence (taught without dividing it into parts in the context of the development of oral speech) is a typical sentence; sentence is a ready sentence;
3. Grammatical unity is a phenomenon of morphology; syntax event.
4. Pronunciation unit — from the minimum phonetic sound-phoneme to the intonation (tone) of sentences;
5. Orthography (spelling) unit - letter; letter combination; word; elements of word formation, form formation and sentence formation; changing and unchanging forms of the word.

We can see that each teacher is guided by his personal experience in choosing working methods and styles in teaching grammar. However, based on the results of experimental and practical work, we can say that the use of various techniques within the framework of communicative, inductive, deductive methods gives positive results and undoubtedly helps to increase the effectiveness of grammar teaching.

The goal of teaching a foreign language with communicative methodology in the field of language is to teach communication in a foreign language in oral and written form within the speech situation. It is known that the method of oral-speech communication is speech. The purpose of teaching speech at school is to develop students' ability to communicate in different situations. Creative activity develops in the process of activity with a creative nature, which forces students to learn and wonder, to find solutions in non-standard situations. If a student likes to speak, read, listen to speech in a foreign language, learn new things, then we can say that he is interested in the subject of "foreign language" and the conditions are created for a certain success. In addition to learning a foreign language, students will have the opportunity to develop their personality, develop skills necessary for future professional activities and communication with other people in everyday life.

In conclusion, we need to explain grammar to students in a deeper and better way, because the young future generation should master the language well and apply it correctly. If we explain grammar through the methods listed above, we will achieve our goal.

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